

Rewarding research participants: Alternative forms of non-financial compensation

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Publication of the International Society of Psychology, Counselling and Education

Research participants are recruited at various levels of higher education for behavioural research. However, financial forms of compensation dominate, despite some research demonstrating the value of non-financial forms. A subset of research participants appears primarily motivated by non-financial forms of compensation. Regardless of this, non-financial forms of compensation are undefined and infrequent. There is a limited amount of literature demonstrating participants' preference for non-financial forms of compensation. One method of identifying and developing non-financial forms of compensation is introduced, based on emphasising participants' experience of the research aim in some capacity. Examples are provided of how non-financial forms of compensation can be developed. Educators are encouraged to further explore the development of this form of compensation for their own research and that of their students, as it may represent the only viable compensation method for many students. The development of different forms of non-financial compensation can lead to academics and students alike experiencing increased participation rates in their research.

Keywords: compensation; financial incentives; non-financial incentives; participant motivation; research participation

Research participants are an integral part of the scientific process. In fact, without their participation, a large proportion of experimental research in psychology would be unfeasible (Clark, 2010). This, combined with the time and effort participants put into physically taking part in research, makes them worthy of compensation. However, the exact form this compensation takes varies not only by type (a shopping voucher versus a cash amount) but also by quantity (a £5 cash reward vs a £20 cash reward) and by country (Dickert et al., 2002; Fry et al., 2005; Peel et al., 2006). As reported by Dickert et al. (2002) in a study on participant compensation policies in 32 US research organisations, only 37.5% of organisations had written guidelines for compensating participants. Despite the relatively large fluctuations in the type and amount of compensation given to participants, they remain, for the most part, in the remit of financial compensation (Fry et al., 2005).

Although financial compensation is the dominant form of compensation provided to participants, some research has shown that it is not the main motivator for participants to take part in research studies. For instance, Clark (2010) distinguishes between motivating factors that influence someone to participate in research at the individual and collective levels. At the individual level, there exist motivating factors such as subjective interest, enjoyment, curiosity, therapeutic interest, material interest, and financial interest. At the collective level, there exist motivating factors such as representation, political empowerment, and informing 'change'. While financial compensation can function as a strong motivating factor for many individuals considering taking part in research, a growing but limited body of research suggests that financial compensation is not the only motivating factor (Clark, 2010; Peel et al., 2006). This may come as no surprise to some readers, many of whom can draw on anecdotal accounts of interacting with participants who explicitly state that their motivation for taking part in a research study has nothing to do with any form of compensation. Rather, factors such as the experience or general interest in the research topic are highlighted as the key motivators.

Therefore, the question arises: what is the most appropriate form of compensation for participants who are not interested in financial compensation? It may be the case that these participants are currently being compensated financially, regardless of their preferences. However, if a non-financial form of compensation can be provided to these participants, it may be worth exploring—especially in instances where researchers struggle to find the resources to sufficiently compensate participants financially. Lawton et al. (2003) investigated participants' motivations for taking part in a 20-year-long study on the effects of intensive blood glucose and blood pressure control on the development of complications in patients with type 2 diabetes. They identified personal health benefits as the main motivating factor. In effect, some participants are motivated to take part in certain research studies because of the possibility of benefitting from the study's objectives. Consequently, a form of compensation valued by some research participants can, in part, be derived from the objectives of the study. For example, participants involved in research on the clinical benefits of a new exploratory treatment for a chronic condition may be motivated by the prospect of successfully treating their condition through the study's exploratory treatment protocol.

However, research involving non-clinical patients also demonstrates a clear preference for non-financial forms of compensation. Peel et al. (2006) analysed participants' reasons for taking part in a research study exploring newly diagnosed patients' perceptions of diabetic service provisions in Scotland. The researchers identified four main themes for why individuals participated in the study: (a) recruitment within health contexts ("the nurse said it would help"), (b) altruism ("if it can help somebody"), (c) qualitative research being seen as inherently innocuous ("nothing to lose"), and (d) therapeutic aspects of interviewing ("getting it off my chest"). Most importantly, no themes were found relating to financial compensation. This is not to say that non-financial compensation is generally the preferred form of compensation, but rather that a form of non-financial compensation is explicitly preferred by some participants.

For example, Warburton and Dyer (2004) found that when investigating older individuals who signed up to volunteer for a range of studies via the University of Queensland's research registry system, four main motivations were identified for why such participants decided to participate in research studies: (a) contribution to the community and science, (b) participation in real research, (c) meeting other people, and (d) learning about the university environment. One thing to note is that these studies varied across a large range of different research topics and did not solely focus on one research area. Elaborating on conclusions drawn from Lawton et al. (2003) and Peel et al. (2006), these findings further emphasise that there exists a form of non-financial compensation that is explicitly preferred by some participants, irrespective of the nature of the study.

It may seem reasonable to assume that non-financial compensation is more appropriate for research studies on specific subjects, such as clinical research, for certain participants, as suggested by Peel et al. (2006). In these instances, the prospect of being provided with the opportunity to find a treatment for a diagnosed condition may naturally be more appealing to sufferers of the condition than financial compensation. However, a more general and relevant question here is how significant financial compensation is in research studies. As Fry et al. (2005) showed, the median cash compensation amount for participants in university studies was \$20 (approximately £16). In which case, is a cash compensation of \$20 (~£16) for a 60–120-minute study a truly significant amount, especially given the current cost of living in many parts of the world? In many cases, the financial compensation provided does not even cover the cost of travel to the study location. In which case, are such participants motivated by financial compensation at all, or are they primarily motivated by some other non-financial compensation?

If the answer is the latter, another question arises: how can participants be motivated by a form of compensation that is not explicitly identified by the researcher? The exact process of identification in this instance is irrelevant to the discussion. What is relevant is that participants may be able to identify a non-financial form of compensation within a particular research study that has not been identified and leveraged by the researcher themselves. Assuming that there exists a non-financial form of compensation that can be derived from a given research study, if it is not identified and explicitly stated by the researcher, a large proportion of potential participants who would have taken part in the research study for that explicit non-financial compensation will not participate. Determining whether any form of non-financial compensation exists will then become the responsibility of participants, who may or may not succeed in doing so.

An in-depth discussion of what is and what is not appropriate financial compensation is beyond the scope of this article. Instead, the focus is on whether a form of compensation exists that is non-financial, is sought out by many participants, and may be perceived as more valuable than many current forms of financial compensation. If so, what is it? If this can be determined, it could serve as a more significant form of compensation for some research participants – one that may also be more easily distributed to participants than financial items. This, in turn, could increase participation rates. Based on the limited literature available on this topic and my own experience as an academic in psychology, I believe that the answer to this question lies in emphasising participants' experience of the research aim in some capacity.

When advertising a research study in psychology, students and academics alike highlight the key features of their research study to prospective participants. One such feature is the overarching aim of the research study. Essentially, participants are told why the research study is being conducted. I believe that this is the most significant statement to prospective participants not interested in financial compensation. Such individuals decide whether to participate in a research study based on more nuanced features of the study, unrelated to financial compensation that can largely be derived from the study's aim.

For example, in Lawton et al.'s (2003) study, participants who were themselves diabetic were actively motivated to take part in a research study on diabetes because of the prospect of being beneficiaries of the study's aim of trying to minimise complications in diabetic patients. In effect, some individuals choose to participate in a research study because they want to experience some aspect of the study identified in its aim. As mentioned, this could be minimising complications in diabetics. However, it can extend to all research topics. The key feature here is that the compensation provided to participants involves emphasising participants' experience of the research aim in some capacity.

How this is specifically communicated to participants can vary. However, I argue that compensation is more impactful when it is tangible and can be possessed by participants. As such, any attempt at emphasising participants' experience of the research aim ought to be a tangible account of this. Below are a few simplified suggestions on how this type of non-financial compensation can be produced based on different research topics: (1) If the aim of the research study is to identify factors contributing to overall workplace dissatisfaction, participants can be provided with a relevant report on how variables in the conducted study are believed or not believed to be contributing factors; (2) If the aim of the research study is to explore how two different nutritional diets directly impact energy expenditure, participants can be provided with a personalised report on how the different diets impacted their own energy expenditure; (3) If the aim of the research study is to devise a training protocol to reduce negative inter-group perceptions, participants can be provided with before and after results detailing any change in their inter-group perceptions in the conducted study and its wider implications.

I believe that this alternative type of compensation represents a more widely accessible form of compensation that can be used by psychologists at all levels. A problem is that largely postgraduates and tenured academics have the resources and necessary funding to give financial compensation. For undergraduate students, things are more complicated. Many do not have the financial resources or ethical clearance to provide financial compensation. However, these students can provide alternative non-financial compensation, which may be even more enticing than financial compensation for many participants. This is especially true of those who are primarily motivated by non-financial forms of compensation.

Guiding senior undergraduate students on how to create alternative non-financial forms of compensation emphasising participants experiencing the research aim, in some capacity, is a productive exercise for any research methods course in psychology. Where students are taught on the different ways of recruiting research participants (volunteer sampling, snowball sampling etc.), if different forms of participant compensation exist that can have an impact on participant recruitment rates, students should know of this. Not only so, but students should be trained on how to create alternative forms of compensation, such as those mentioned in this article. Students can be guided through a series of exercises or workshops on the different forms of participant compensation that exist, financial and non-financial, and their appropriateness and viability for different research studies and researchers. Then, in the context of non-financial compensation emphasising participants experiencing the research aim, in some capacity, students can engage in a variety of exercises where they attempt to create appropriate forms of this compensation for their own research project.

However, while providing financial compensation aligns with the motivations of some individuals participating in research, non-financial compensation, as discussed in this paper, does not align with the motives of others. Nonetheless, non-financial forms of compensation for research participants merit further serious exploration by the academic community, as they satisfy the motivations that

many participants have for taking part in research studies. In combination with more conventional forms of financial compensation, they can appeal to and motivate even more individuals to participate in crucial research studies, ultimately increasing participation rates.

Finally, alternative non-financial compensation for research participants also provides a viable and educational way for psychology students to develop materials that offer a form of compensation to their participants – who would otherwise receive none if financial compensation were the only option. This, too, can contribute to increased participation rates.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

REFERENCES

- Clark, T. (2010). On “being researched”: Why do people engage with qualitative research? *Qualitative Research, 10*(4), 399–419. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794110366796>
- Dickert, N., Emanuel, E., & Grady, C. (2002). Paying research subjects: An analysis of current policies. *Annals of Internal Medicine, 136*(5), 368–373.
- Fry, C. L., Ritter, A., Baldwin, S., Bowen, K. J., Gardiner, P., Holt, T., Jenkinson, R., & Johnston, J. (2005). Paying research participants: A study of current practices in Australia. *Journal of Medical Ethics, 31*(9), 542–547.
- Lawton, J., Fox, A., Fox, C., & Kinmonth, A. L. (2003). Participating in the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS): A qualitative study of patients’ experiences. *British Journal of General Practice, 53*(490), 394–398.
- Peel, E., Parry, O., Douglas, M., & Lawton, J. (2006). “It’s no skin off my nose”: Why people take part in qualitative research. *Qualitative Health Research, 16*(10), 1335–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732306294511>
- Warburton, J., & Dyer, M. (2004). Older volunteers participating in a university research registry: Helping others my age. *Educational Gerontology, 30*(5), 367–381.